

MODERN APPROACHES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF UZBEKISTAN TO GREEN ECONOMY

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Annotation. *The article presents the modern approaches of the development of Uzbekistan to the green economy, reforms and measures taken by the government of the country regarding the transition to a “green” economy, promotion of a “green” and inclusive model of sustainable economic growth. In addition, issues related to climate change are discussed, which negatively affect environmental and food security, and the eradication of poverty.*

Key words: *green economy, environmental factors, natural resources, sustainable development.*

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada O‘zbekistonni yashil iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishga zamonaviy yondashuvlar, mamlakat hukumati tomonidan “yashil” iqtisodiyotga o‘tish bo‘yicha amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlar va chora-tadbirlar, barqaror iqtisodiy o‘shining “yashil” va inklyuziv modelini rag‘batlantirish haqida muhokama qilinida. Bundan tashqari, atrof-muhit va oziq-ovqat xavfsizligiga salbiy ta‘sir ko‘rsatuvchi iqlim o‘zgarishi, qashshoqlikka barham berish masalalari muhokama qilinadi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *yashil iqtisodiyot, ekologik omillar, tabiiy resurslar, barqaror rivojlanish.*

In order to implement the tasks defined in the development strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, to increase the effectiveness of measures taken to ensure “green” and inclusive economic growth, as well as the further expansion of the use of renewable energy sources and resource conservation in all sectors of the economy, the strategic transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to a “green” economy has been approved and substantiated. Studying the features annually as a result of human activity in the world, 20 billion tons of carbon dioxide are emitted into the atmosphere and more than 300 million tons of plastic waste are produced. The global emissions on the planet of Earth continue to grow. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), about 99 percent of the world's population breathes air whose quality parameters exceed the maximum permissible values and threaten human health, and more than tens of millions of annual deaths worldwide are attributed to environmental causes, including air pollution. Harmful levels of fine particulate matter and nitrogen dioxide are mainly due to the combustion of fossil fuels. The Earth is experiencing a global energy crisis, a cost-of-living crisis, a food crisis, wars, droughts and famines. Extreme weather events such as tropical cyclones, desertification and sea level rise caused by climate change cause enormous damage to countries. The increased frequency of natural disasters is a result of increasing greenhouse gas emissions.

The issues related to climate change negatively affect environmental and food security, and the eradication of poverty. Based on this, Uzbekistan pays great attention to reducing the impact of climate change and adapting to it, accelerating measures to transition to a “green” economy, promoting a “green” and inclusive model of economic growth. In Uzbekistan, 2025 has been declared the Year of Environmental Protection and “Green” Economy. The green

economy is an important area aimed at protecting the environment and ensuring balanced economic development.

The primary task of the transition to a green economy is a responsible attitude of people to the Earth's resources. The society faces the goal of finding a reasonable compromise between increasing well-being and preserving natural resources. One of the principles of a green economy is state support for stable production and consumption, as well as the introduction of low-carbon resource-saving technologies.

The transition to a green economy ensures Uzbekistan's active participation in the fight against global climate change and the implementation of priority policies aimed at the well-being of the population. At the second global summit “Partnership for green growth and the 2030 global goals” in South Korea in 2021, the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev said: “We can no longer ignore the signals that nature itself is sending us. Unfortunately, climate change is accelerating. No one doubts anymore that countries’ actions to achieve green development goals must be more active and more effective. We have no other choice”. The fossil fuels such as coal, oil, and gas are the largest contributors to global climate change. They account for more than 75 percent of global greenhouse gas emissions and nearly 90 percent of all carbon dioxide emissions. Much of the greenhouse gases that cover the Earth and trap the sun’s heat are produced during energy production, when fossil fuels are burned to generate electricity and heat. The fossil fuels still account for more than 80 percent of global energy production.

Energy is currently the foundation of the climate problem and the key to solving it. According to expert research, the scientific evidence clearly shows that to avoid the worst impacts of climate change, emissions must be cut almost in half by 2030 and reach net zero emissions by 2050. To achieve this, scientists state that they had to invest in alternative energy sources that are clean, accessible, affordable, sustainable and reliable. UN Secretary-general António Guterres said that was time to stop burning our planet’s resources and start investing in the renewable energy that’s all around us. The renewable energy sources, which are abundant around us from the sun, wind, water, waste and the Earth’s heat, are naturally replenished, emit virtually no greenhouse gases or pollutants into the atmosphere and are, in most cases, cheaper than coal, oil or gas.

Investing in renewable energy and energy efficiency will be cheaper, create more jobs and produce far less pollution than burning more gas, oil and coal. The International renewable energy agency (IRENA) estimates that by 2050, more than 90 percent of the world’s electricity can and should come from renewable sources. By 2030, cheap electricity from renewable sources could provide 65 percent of the world’s electricity supply. This would capture and decarbonize 90 percent of the carbon dioxide (CO₂) and other greenhouse gases (GHGs) emitted into the atmosphere, such as methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O) and fluorinated gases (F-gases). The energy sector, significantly reduces carbon emissions and helping to mitigate climate change (decarbonization is the process of reducing the carbon levels of industries and the economy) by 2050. In the energy sector, decarbonization is critical to reducing greenhouse gas emissions and reducing dependence on fossil fuels. One of the main methods of decarbonization is the transition to nano- and alternative energy sources such as solar, wind, hydro and geothermal energy).

The IEA estimates that the transition to zero emissions will lead to an overall increase in jobs in the energy sector. For example, while about 5 million jobs could be lost in fossil fuel production by 2030, the number of jobs in clean energy will increase by about 14 million, resulting in a net gain of 9 million jobs. In addition, energy-related industries will require tens of

millions of additional workers to perform new functions in the production of electric vehicles and ultra-efficient appliances, or to apply the innovative technologies such as hydrogen technology. This means that by 2030, a total of more than 30 million jobs could be created in the areas of using clean energy technologies that provide high efficiency and low emissions.

The green technologies are now becoming a key element in reducing carbon emissions and minimizing the effects of climate change. According the UN studies investments in the amount of \$1.8 trillion by 2030 can bring more than \$7 trillion in net benefits. The green technological solutions that combine the use of wind and hydrogen can not only reduce emissions by 80 million tons of CO₂ annually, but also ensure the stability of energy supply in the regions.

In recent years, a number of important measures aimed at developing a green economy have been implemented in Uzbekistan. The laws “On the use of renewable energy sources”, “On hydrometeorological activities”, “Concept of environmental protection of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030”, “Strategy for the transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to “green” economy for the period 2019-2030 have been adopted. In 2023-2024, the green energy certificate system was introduced to control the quality of products and processes produced using environmentally friendly technologies and renewable energy sources, and much more.

By 2030, greenhouse gas emissions in Uzbekistan should be reduced by 35% per unit of GDP. This ambitious commitment under the Paris agreement was reaffirmed at the 27th Conference of the parties to the UN Framework convention on climate change in November 2022 in Sharm el-Sheikh, Egypt. It was noted that Uzbekistan is ready for active cooperation with the international community aimed at ensuring safe and sustainable development, building a climate for a sustainable future.

Thus, according to the government of Uzbekistan, economic progress will be achieved through the implementation of the principles of green economy. The priority in this direction is low-carbon development and resource conservation in all sectors of the economy, the introduction of efficient and environmentally friendly technologies.

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